

Time-Varying Volatility and Asymmetric Effects : An Empirical Investigation of the Indian FMCG and Financial Services Sector

Paper Id : 20692 Submission Date : 2025-09-01 Acceptance Date : 2025-09-21 Publication Date : 2025-09-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.1769514

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Abstract

This research aims to analyse the time-varying volatility, asymmetric effects, and the leverage effects of the NIFTY FMCG and Financial Services stocks by using the GARCH, EGARCH, and TGARCH models. A study using daily stock returns from 2015 to 2024 shows that financial services stocks have higher volatility persistence, while FMCG stocks are more stable. Also, the results show that asymmetric effects occur, with financial stocks responding more strongly to negative shocks than FMCG stocks. The leverage effect in financial services has an immense impact that makes risk exposure higher, but FMCG stocks stay safe. These findings help policymakers and investors understand sectoral risk, which has effects on managing portfolios and keeping the economy stable.

Keywords

Time-varying volatility, Asymmetric Volatility, Leverage Effect, GARCH Models.

Introduction

Stock market volatility has been unusual in the context of economic globalisation, especially in the wake of the current global financial crisis (Bhowmik and Wang 522). This volatility study is difficult since everyone interprets it differently. However, Mullins described it in straightforward and uncomplicated terms: volatility is the extent to which the price of an asset, commodity, or market rises or falls during a small period. As volatility impacts numerous economic and financial applications, including asset pricing, risk and return analysis, and portfolio optimisation, it is a particularly important subject (Ali et al. 1098). In addition to serving as a gauge of market efficiency, volatility in the stock market is a crucial component of risk management and investing choices (Villar-Rubio et al. 500-509). To better understand how financial markets react to outside shocks, time-varying volatility has drawn a lot of attention in the field of finance research (Ali et al. 1098). The "time-varying volatility" refers to the volatility of asset returns that fluctuates over multiple periods (Rana, 15-34).

The NIFTY Financial Services and NIFTY Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) indices present the two important sectors of the Indian stock market. With a weightage of 36.53%, the NIFTY Financial Services sector is the largest from the service side, while the NIFTY Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) sector leads the manufacturing sector with a weightage of 7.63% ("Nifty 50"). The sectors exhibit considerable divergence in market risk exposure; financial stocks are acutely responsive to economic policies and global market dynamics, while FMCG equities are deemed defensive owing to their consistent consumer demand.

The present research uses Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) models and its modified versions, Threshold GARCH (TGARCH) and Exponential GARCH (EGARCH), to assess volatility in these sectors. For the first time, Engle (1987-1007) suggested modelling time-varying conditional variance using the ARCH process, which models the series' variances using historical disruption and permits the error term's variance to change with time, which Bollerslev (1986) eventually expanded into the GARCH model, enabling a more thorough examination of volatility clustering (307-327). Since then, a lot of people have been using the GARCH family of models to predict future volatility and evaluate market risk.

This investigation also examines the asymmetric effects in the NIFTY FMCG and NIFTY Financial Services indices, while also documenting time-varying volatility. Stock markets have been extensively studied regarding the asymmetric return-volatility effect (Bollerslev et al. 353-384, Bollerslev et al.151-161). This volatility asymmetry indicates that the impact of negative and positive market disruptions on stock returns differs (Ormos and Timotity). (Nelson 347-370) proposed the Exponential GARCH (EGARCH) model, which accounts for the asymmetries in the

effects of positive and negative shocks on volatility. In Zakoian introduced the TGARCH (Threshold GARCH) model to address the observed asymmetry in volatility within financial markets (931-955). By including threshold variables in the conditional variance equation, the TGARCH model accommodates varying responses to both positive and negative shocks (Glosten et al. 1779–1801). Utilizing these models, this study aims to quantify the degree of leverage effects in the stocks of the FMCG and Financial Services sectors.

The findings from this study are useful to economists, investors, and policymakers. Investors use volatility modeling to protect themselves from market uncertainty and maximize asset allocation. Policymakers create regulatory frameworks that improve the stability of financial markets by using volatility trends. Assessments of sectoral volatility help financial experts make well-informed forecasts about future market movements. This study contributes to a better understanding of sectoral risk dynamics by examining time-varying volatility in the FMCG and Financial Services sectors, which helps stakeholders make strategic financial decisions.

Objective of study

1. To analyse the time-varying volatility in the stocks of NIFTY Financial Services and NIFTY FMCG indices using GARCH, EGARCH, and TGARCH models.
2. Examine the asymmetric effects of market shocks on volatility and assess the differential impact of positive and negative shocks.
3. Quantify leverage effects in the Financial Services and FMCG sectors to determine the disproportionate influence of negative shocks.

Review of Literature

This section explains the previous studies related to stock market volatility, the time-varying effect of volatility on the stock market, the asymmetric effect of market shocks on volatility and how GARCH Models are used in the sectoral volatility analysis:

Stock Market Volatility

A crucial component of financial markets that has attracted a lot of interest from both scholars and industry professionals is the volatility of stock returns (Orabi and Alqurran). Volatility can be defined as the difference between the past and present values of stock returns, shows how unsure the returns are and is an important tool for managing portfolios, figuring out risk, and setting prices for derivatives (Gupta and Mishra). In today's fast-changing financial world, investors and policymakers need to be able to accurately predict market volatility (Boudri and Bouhadi 300). Because there are more financial risks, researchers have made several models that can track and identify volatility trends. There are some mixed results from the studies.

Some say that simple models make the most accurate predictions if the market is stable and the volatility follows a trend that can be predicted (Kundlia and Gakhar). For example, Poon and Granger looked at several different ways to predict volatility and found that easy methods, like historical volatility and moving averages, often do as well or better than more complex models, especially when the market is stable (478-539).

Others say that complicated models like ARCH models are better, Hansen and Lunde looked at a lot of different volatility models and discovered that complex models, like longmemory and nonlinear models, are often better at catching market changes than simple models (873-889). Bollerslev created the GARCH model, which showed that over time, financial data shows volatility grouping that simple models can't show (307-327). Along the same lines, Nelson created the EGARCH model, which considers the leverage effect (347-370). This effect says that negative shocks are stronger than positive shocks of the same size when it comes to volatility. These models are now important in the field of financial econometrics because they let us study how volatility persists and how clustering effects affect stock markets.

Time-varying Volatility Effect

There are differences in volatility between industry sectors because of how the market works, how sensitive the economy is, and the types of foreign risk factors that affect the market. Prices change more often in some areas, like energy, technology, and commodities, because they are more affected by global economic trends, geopolitical threats, and imbalances in supply and demand (Engle and Rangel 1187–1222). Research shows that industries that depend on raw materials, foreign trade, or government rules have higher volatility persistence than more stable industries (Pindyck, 1-27). For example, oil price shocks, environmental rules, and geopolitical tensions can have a big effect on the energy industry, which can cause big changes in stock returns (Sadorsky 449–469). In the same way, the technology sector is very unstable because of the speed with

which new technologies are introduced, the close watch of regulators, and shifting customer tastes (Shiller 49-60). GARCH family models show that these sectors have volatility clustering and uneven effects, meaning that negative shocks (like crackdowns on regulations or problems in the supply chain) tend to make volatility rise more than positive shocks (Hammoudeh and Li 152–171). The commodity market is another one where global changes in supply and demand, changes in the value of the dollar, and extreme weather events have a big effect on instability (Tang and Xiong 54–74). Prices of agricultural goods, metals, and energy commodities often have "longmemory effects," which means that times of high volatility last for a long time. It has been shown that GARCH, EGARCH, and TGARCH models are better at predicting volatility in commodity markets than standard time-series models (Bollerslev et al. 353–384).

Asymmetric Effects of Market Shocks on Volatility

When it comes to financial markets, bad news tends to make them more volatile than good news of the same size. This is called asymmetric volatility. A lot of research on finance has written about this effect, which is called the leverage effect (Black 177-181, Nelson 347-370). Nelson came up with the Exponential GARCH (EGARCH) model, which takes this unevenness into account by letting positive and negative shocks have different effects (347-370). There is strong proof of asymmetric volatility in financial stocks in emerging markets like India. This means that bad shocks have a bigger effect on market uncertainty (Ormos and Timotity). Zakoian came up with the Threshold GARCH (TGARCH) model, which improves volatility modeling even more by adding threshold effects (931-955). In this model, negative returns cause volatility to respond more strongly than positive returns. Studies that use TGARCH models have found that leverage has big effects on the stock market, especially when the economy is bad (Glosten et al. 1779-1801, Bollerslev et al. 353-384).

Methodology

The purpose of this research is to use GARCH-family models to examine time-varying volatility in the NIFTY FMCG and NIFTY Financial Services indices. To ascertain the overstated effect of negative shocks, it also assesses the implications of asymmetric volatility and measures leverage effects.

Data Description

The data is obtained from investing.com and the National Stock Exchange (NSE) from 1 January 2015 to 31 December 2024. The dataset contains the daily closing price of stocks from Nifty Financial Services (Large cap), i.e. HDFC Bank (HDBK), Axis Bank (AXBK), ICICI Bank (ICBK), Kotak Bank (Kotak), Bajfinance (BJFN), Shriramfinance (SHMF), Indusbank (INSIN), Bjaifinservices (BJFS). SBIN, HDFC Life, and SBILIFE are excluded from the study because of the non-availability of data. And the Log return of NIFTY FMCG Stock, i.e. ITC, Nestleind (NEST), TATA Consum (TACN), Britannia (BRIT), Hindunilvr (HUNL).

Log return was calculated by using the formula:

$$R_t = \ln (P_t / P_{t-1})$$

Here, R_t is the log return at time t , P_t is the closing price of the current year, and P_{t-1} is the closing price of the previous year.

Using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, the return series was checked to ensure it was stationary. All return series were confirmed to be stationary, allowing for further econometric modelling.

Methodology : This study uses the following econometric models to examine asymmetric impacts and volatility patterns:

Unit Root Test

The stationarity of the log return series is checked using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test before volatility models are applied. To accurately represent volatility, the ADF test makes sure that the return series is free of unit roots. The alternative hypothesis of the ADF test verifies stationarity, whereas the null hypothesis asserts that the series has a unit root (is nonstationary).

Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) Model

Bollerslev developed the conventional GARCH (1,1) model, which models conditional variance as follows to capture time-varying volatility:

$$\sigma_t^2 = \omega + \alpha \varepsilon_{t-1}^2 + \beta \sigma_{t-1}^2$$

where σ_t^2 represents the conditional variance at the time, a constant, α measures the impact of past squared residuals, and β represents the persistence of volatility (307-327).

Exponential GARCH (EGARCH) Model

Nelson, developed the EGARCH model, which accounts for asymmetric effects on volatility. The way it is stated is:

$$\log(\sigma_t^2) = \omega + \beta \log(\sigma_{t-1}^2) + \alpha \frac{\varepsilon_{t-1}}{\sigma_{t-1}} + \gamma \left(\left| \frac{\varepsilon_{t-1}}{\sigma_{t-1}} \right| - E \left| \frac{\varepsilon_{t-1}}{\sigma_{t-1}} \right| \right)$$

Here γ indicates whether negative shocks cause more volatility than positive shocks, capturing the leverage impact (347-370).

Threshold GARCH (TGARCH) Model

The TGARCH (1,1) model is used to investigate the asymmetric impact of market shocks in more detail. This model was first proposed by Zakoian (931-955). It is stated as:

$$\sigma_t^2 = \omega + \alpha \varepsilon_{t-1}^2 + \gamma D_{t-1} \varepsilon_{t-1}^2 + \beta \sigma_{t-1}^2$$

Here, D_{t-1} is a dummy variable that, in the case of negative shocks, takes the value of 1; otherwise, it takes the value of 0. A statistically significant γ result suggests that volatility is more affected by negative shocks than by positive shocks.

Result and Discussion

In this part, the study's findings are shown. These include Descriptive Statistics, which describes the sample data's main statistical properties; Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test for Sample Stocks, which checks whether the log returns are stationary; and Empirical Analysis of Time-Varying Volatility and Asymmetric Effects in NIFTY Financial Services and FMCG Stocks, which looks into how volatility changes over time using GARCH, EGARCH, and TGARCH models to find time-dependent volatility patterns, asymmetric effects, and leverage effects.

Descriptive Statistics

To understand the distributional characteristics of returns, descriptive statistics are computed before the implementation of volatility models. Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for log returns of NIFTY Financial Services and NIFTY FMCG stocks. The key metrics include mean, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis, and the Jarque-Bera test for normality.

Table1: Descriptive Statistics of Log Returns

Stock	Mean	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis	Jarque- Bera	Probability
ITC	-0.000255	0.016178	0.471128	11.00757	6704.055	0.0000
NEST	-0.000505	0.014528	-0.379494	8.609615	3301.398	0.0000
TACN	-0.000729	0.019245	0.157581	8.827738	3512.684	0.0000
BRIT	-0.000666	0.014572	-0.028064	10.97320	6555.876	0.0000
HUNL	-0.000453	0.013704	-0.655377	13.66022	4816.625	0.0000
HDBK	-0.000532	0.017936	0.340813	30.51601	11779.83	0.0000
AXBK	-0.000303	0.021932	1.129184	11.09944	7876.72	0.0000
ICBK	-0.00056	0.019844	0.16401	10.82636	8192.386	0.0000
KOTAK	-0.000421	0.016616	0.307784	18.82371	6556.660	0.0000
BJFN	-0.0012	0.022915	0.6097	13.24741	12278.19	0.0000
SHMF	-0.0004	0.027135	0.44511	39.26444	8521.765	0.0000
INSIN	-0.00077	0.025159	0.078757	30.44156	15860.2	0.0000
BJFS	-0.00101	0.021156	1.024263	21.55159	35924.9	0.0000

Source: Author own source.

The table of descriptive data offers an insightful analysis of the risk and return properties of particular FMCG and financial services stocks. Since the mean log returns for every stock are unfavourable from this, it is clear that these equities have declined on average over the recorded period. Among these, Bajaj Finance BJFN and BJFS have the greatest percentage of negative returns, implying more risk than other companies. By contrast, FMCG firms such as ITC, NEST, and HUL have rather lower negative returns, thereby stressing their stability about the stocks of banks.

Compared to their FMCG counterparts, Financial Services companies exhibit much higher volatility, as measured by the standard deviation (S.D.). The biggest standard deviation is found in stocks like BJFN, BJFS, and SHMF, indicating their higher level of risk. However, FMCG firms like ITC, NEST, and HUL have significantly less volatility, which supports their position as safe equities with more consistent price movements.

The skewness analysis indicates that Financial Services equities, including AXBK, BJFS and BJFN, are positively skewed. This suggests that large positive returns occur more frequently than large negative ones. On the other hand, FMCG stocks, including HUL, NEST, and BRIT, demonstrate negative skewness, which suggests that small losses are more prevalent than significant gains. The kurtosis values for all stocks are substantially greater than 3, suggesting leptokurtic distributions with fat tails. This implies that these equities are more susceptible to sudden market shocks than those with a normal distribution, as extreme price movements (both positive and negative) are more prevalent. The extreme kurtosis of financial stocks, particularly SHMF (39.26), HDBK (30.51), and BJFS (21.55) indicate a higher frequency of rapid price fluctuations.

By denying the null hypothesis of normality, the Jarque-Bera test for normality confirms that none of the return distributions are normal, as all probability values are 0.000. This demonstrates the necessity of employing sophisticated volatility models, including GARCH, EGARCH, and TGARCH, to more accurately represent the time-varying volatility and risk associated with these equities. Generally, the results indicate that FMCG stocks are relatively stable, with reduced volatility and fewer extreme movements, whereas Financial Services stocks are highly volatile and prone to significant fluctuations, making them riskier investment options.

ADF Test for the Sample Stocks

It is crucial to test data for stationarity in studies where the underlying variables are time-based (Mushtaq). A time series that exhibits constant statistical characteristics across time is said to be stationary. One popular statistical technique for determining whether or not a series is stationary is the ADF test, which looks for unit roots in time series data (Dickey and Fuller 427-431). In the ADF test, the alternative hypothesis claims that the time series is stationary, while the null hypothesis asserts that the series has a unit root, demonstrating non-stationarity (Guo 101-106). The null hypothesis is rejected for all stocks because the p-values of the given stocks are significantly lower to 0.05, and the ADF test statistics are below the critical levels at the 5% (-2.8625) level as shown in table 2. This demonstrates the stationarity of the log return series, which qualifies them for additional econometric modelling, including volatility analysis using GARCH, EGARCH, and TGARCH.

Table 2 ADF Test Results

Stock log return	ADF Test Statistics	Critical Value (5%)	p- value
ITC	-51.3367	-2.8625	0.0001
NEST	-51.8579	-2.8625	0.0001
TACN	-51.5008	-2.8625	0.0001
BRIT	-49.4952	-2.8625	0.0001
HUNL	-52.1648	-2.8625	0.0001
HDBK	-36.901	-2.8625	0
AXBK	-49.5937	-2.8625	0.0001
ICBK	-50.1994	-2.8625	0.0001
KOTAK	-52.11843	-2.8625	0.0001
BJFN	-49.90527	-2.8625	0.0001
SHMF	-48.37	-2.8625	0.0001
INSIN	-23.1248	-2.8625	0
BJFS	-48.37815	-2.8625	0.0001

Source: Authors own source.

Empirical Analysis of Time-Varying Volatility and Asymmetric Effects in NIFTY Financial Services and FMCG Stocks

A comparison method is employed based on the results from the GARCH(1,1), EGARCH(1,1), and TGARCH(1,1) models to fully understand the volatility patterns in the NIFTY Financial Services and FMCG sectors. The results of GARCH(1,1), EGARCH(1,1), and TGARCH(1,1) are reflected in Table 3. This section is bifurcated according to the objectives of the study into three sections i.e. first one is Volatility Persistence, the Second section reveals the results of the Asymmetric impact of market shocks, and the third part reflects the leverage effect of Financial Services and FMCG stocks.

Table 3 The Results of GARCH Model

Stock	Model	Log Likelihood	AIC	ARCH (α)	GARCH (β)	$\alpha + \beta$
ITC (FMCG)	GARCH(1,1)	6844.911	-5.52801	0.15674	0.6870	0.8438
	EGARCH(1,1)	6853.152	-5.53386	0.2485	0.9092	1.1577
	TGARCH(1,1)	6843.443	-5.5274	0.1549	0.6839	0.8388
NEST (FMCG)	GARCH(1,1)	7120.617	-5.75802	0.07432	0.8830	0.9574
	EGARCH(1,1)	7127.59	-5.7438	0.15621	0.9682	1.1244
	TGARCH(1,1)	7119.699	-5.75076	0.09289	0.8849	0.9778
TACN (FMCG)	GARCH(1,1)	6404.668	-5.1722	0.1052	0.8164	0.9216
	EGARCH(1,1)	6425.865	-5.18858	0.141	0.975	1.116
	TGARCH(1,1)	6405.099	-5.173	0.08472	81993	81993
BRIT (FMCG)	GARCH(1,1)	7026.518	5.6747	0.19996	0.6762	0.8762
	EGARCH(1,1)	7028.674	-5.6756	0.36871	0.8679	1.2366
	TGARCH(1,1)	7035.363	-5.6745	0.2323	0.6711	0.9035
HUNL (FMCG)	GARCH(1,1)	7231.342	-5.84028	0.11655	0.8034	0.92
	EGARCH(1,1)	7234.085	-5.8416	0.1917	0.9544	1.1461
	TGARCH(1,1)	7229.727	-5.8397	0.1382	0.7993	0.9375
HDBK (Financial service)	GARCH(1,1)	7323.41	-5.91467	0.10783	0.8333	0.9412
	EGARCH(1,1)	7314.583	-5.9067	0.17217	0.9672	1.1394
	TGARCH(1,1)	7320.695	-5.91325	0.1001	0.8335	0.9337

AXBK	GARCH(1,1)	6358.464	-5.1349	0.10848	0.8512	0.9597
	EGARCH(1,1)	6367.172	-51411	0.19431	0.9722	1.1666
	TGARCH(1,1)	6357.868	-5.1348	0.07635	0.8576	0.934
ICBK (Financial service)	GARCH(1,1)	6462.943	-5.2193	0.1062	0.8741	0.9803
	EGARCH(1,1)	6487.079	-5.238	0.1739	0.9775	1.1514
	TGARCH(1,1)	6461.449	-5.2186	0.08969	0.8725	0.9622
KOTAK (Financial service)	GARCH(1,1)	6884.355	-5.55988	0.15282	0.7656	0.9184
	EGARCH(1,1)	6893.79	-5.5667	0.24007	0.9470	1.1871
	TGARCH(1,1)	6888.359	-5.5637	0.1416	0.7827	0.9243
BJFN	GARCH(1,1)	6080.886	-4.9106	0.1078	0.8028	0.9106
	EGARCH(1,1)	6092.477	-4.9191	0.16969	0.9620	1.1318
	TGARCH(1,1)	6080.74	-49108	0.0734	0.8131	0.8865
SHMF (Financial service)	GARCH(1,1)	5672.882	-4.5809	0.1107	0.8038	0.9145
	EGARCH(1,1)	5675.94	-4.5825	0.1983	0.9538	1.1521
	TGARCH(1,1)	5669.948	-4.57877	0.1071	0.8038	0.9109
INSIN (Financial service)	GARCH(1,1)	6184.206	-4.9941	0.1749	0.7995	0.9744
	EGARCH(1,1)	6196.615	-5.0033	0.2531	0.9721	1.2253
	TGARCH(1,1)	6186.73	-4.9965	0.10777	0.8237	0.9315
BJFS (Financial service)	GARCH(1,1)	6245.6	-5.04372	0.1869	0.6928	0.8797
	EGARCH(1,1)	6251.408	-5.0476	0.15633	0.9699	1.1262
	TGARCH(1,1)	6245.748	-5.04425	0.12158	0.7236	0.8452

Table: Authors own source

Volatility Persistence

The GARCH(1,1) results show that financial services stocks have significant volatility persistence because a high value for $\alpha + \beta$ close to 1 indicates greater volatility persistence. The β values of stocks like BJFS, HDBK, and ICBK are higher than 0.95, indicating that a volatility impact lasts for a long time. It takes longer for these equities to stabilize because of the nature of the financial sector, where economic policies, investor mood, and market movements all contribute to protracted uncertainty. On the other hand, FMCG stocks like NEST, ITC, and BRIT show lower β values, suggesting that volatility fades faster. According to this, FMCG stocks are less vulnerable to protracted market volatility because of their defensive posture and steady customer demand, which enable them to stay stable even during volatile market times.

Asymmetric Impact of Market Shocks

The EGARCH(1,1) and TGARCH(1,1) models indicate that financial services securities have a significant asymmetric reaction to market shocks. Adverse shocks result in an excessive rise in volatility, highlighting the sector's sensitivity to unfavourable market occurrences. Stocks like HDBK and KOTAK demonstrate strong ARCH (α) values, signifying that historical shocks substantially influence future volatility. This indicates that financial equities respond significantly to adverse news, with volatility enduring for a prolonged duration. Conversely, whereas FMCG stocks display asymmetry, the impact is rather subdued. Adverse shocks in the FMCG sector do not significantly impact volatility

levels, underscoring the defensive characteristics of these equities. This indicates that even in market declines, FMCG equities exhibit enhanced stability, as their demand remains mostly impervious to wider economic variations.

Leverage effect

The TGARCH(1,1) model demonstrates notable leverage effects in financial services equities, namely in ICBK and HUNL, suggesting that adverse market shocks lead to a pronounced rise in risk exposure. This indicates that financial equities are acutely responsive to market declines and economic unpredictability, where negative information can provoke increased volatility and extended instability. The leverage impact in FMCG companies is rather subdued, indicating that negative shocks do not result in significant volatility surges. This underscores the defensive characteristics of the FMCG sector, as these equities exhibit diminished sensitivity to economic changes and sustain relative stability even within market upheaval. Consequently, FMCG companies represent a more secure investment alternative during economic recessions, whereas financial stocks demonstrate increased volatility in reaction to adverse market occurrences.

Conclusion

This research uses GARCH, EGARCH, and TGARCH models to look at how volatility changes over time and how effects are inconsistent in NIFTY Financial Services and FMCG stocks. According to the findings, stocks in financial services have a strong leverage effect because they are more volatile and respond more strongly to negative market shocks. To the contrary, FMCG stocks exhibit less volatility clustering and more stability, which supports the fact that they are protective. This research gives investors and lawmakers useful information for evaluating risk and managing portfolios.

However, the study has some limitations. It only looks at a small group of stocks, so it might not fully show how volatile the sector as a whole is. It also only uses GARCH models, which might not take into account structure breaks or long-memory effects. The results can only be used in certain situations because socioeconomic factors were not included. These holes can be filled in future studies by adding external economic indicators, looking into different volatility models, and applying the analysis to a wider range of industries to get a fuller picture of market risk.

References

1. "Nifty 50." *Nifty Indices*, www.niftyindices.com/indices/equity/broad-based-indices/nifty--50. Accessed 6 Mar. 2025.
2. Ali, Farman, et al. "Modelling Time-Varying Volatility Using GARCH Models: Evidence from the Indian Stock Market." *F1000Research*, vol. 11, 2022, p. 1098.
3. Bhowmik, Roni, and Shouyang Wang. "Stock Market Volatility and Return Analysis: A Systematic Literature Review." *Entropy*, vol. 22, no. 5, 2020, p. 522.
4. Black, Fischer. "Studies of Stock Price Volatility Changes." *Proceedings of the American Statistical Association, Business and Economic Statistics Section*, 1976, pp. 177–181.
5. Bollerslev, Tim, et al. "A Discrete-Time Model for Daily S&P 500 Returns and Realized Variations: Jumps and Leverage Effects." *Journal of Econometrics*, vol. 150, no. 2, 2009, pp. 151–166. doi:10.1016/j.jeconom.2008.12.022.
6. Bollerslev, Tim, et al. "Leverage and Volatility Feedback Effects in High-Frequency Data." *Journal of Financial Econometrics*, vol. 4, no. 3, 2006, pp. 353–384. doi:10.1093/jfinec/nbl002.
7. Bollerslev, Tim. "Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity." *Journal of Econometrics*, vol. 31, no. 3, 1986, pp. 307–327. doi:10.1016/0304-4076(86)90063-1.
8. Boudri, Imane, and Abdellatif El Bouhadi. "Modeling and Forecasting Historical Volatility Using Econometric and Deep Learning Approaches: Evidence from the Moroccan and Bahraini Stock Markets." *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, vol. 17, no. 7, 2024, p. 300. doi:10.3390/jrfm17070300.
9. Dickey, David A., and Wayne A. Fuller. "Distribution of the Estimators for Autoregressive Time Series with a Unit Root." *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, vol. 74, no. 366, 1979, pp. 427–431. doi:10.2307/2286348.
10. Engle, Robert F. "Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity with Estimates of the Variance of United Kingdom Inflation." *Econometrica*, vol. 50, no. 4, 1982, pp. 987–1007. doi:10.2307/1912773.
11. Engle, Robert F., and Jose Gonzalo Rangel. "The Spline-GARCH Model for Low-Frequency Volatility and Its Macroeconomic Causes." *Review of Financial Studies*, vol. 21, no. 3, 2008, pp. 1187–1222.
12. Glosten, Lawrence R., et al. "On the Relation between the Expected Value and the Volatility of the Nominal Excess Return on Stocks." *The Journal of Finance*, vol. 48, no. 5, 1993, pp. 1779–1801. doi:10.1111/j.1540-6261.1993.tb05128.x.
13. Guo, Zhichao. "Research on the Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test for Predicting Stock Prices and Returns." *Advances in Economics Management and Political Sciences*, vol. 44, no. 1, 2023, pp. 101–106. doi:10.54254/2754-1169/44/20232198.

14. Gupta, Anshul, and Radhika Mishra. "A Comprehensive Study of Stock Market Volatility: Types, Determinants, and Measurement Methods." *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, vol. 6, no. 6, 2024. doi:10.36948/ijfmr.2024.v06i06.30054.
15. Hammoudeh, Shawkat M., and Huimin Li. "Oil Sensitivity and Systematic Risk in Oil-Sensitive Stock Indices." *Journal of Economic and Business Research*, vol. 60, no. 2, 2008, pp. 152–171. doi:10.1016/j.jeconbus.2007.06.002.
16. Hansen, Peter R., and Asger Lunde. "A Forecast Comparison of Volatility Models: Does Anything Beat a GARCH(1,1)?" *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, vol. 20, no. 7, 2005, pp. 873–889. doi:10.1002/jae.800.
17. Kundlia, Shivani, and D. V. Gakhar. "Stock Market Volatility Forecasting Models: A Comparative Study." *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 2024. doi:10.2139/ssrn.4832110.
18. Mullins, Gary E. "Stock Market Volatility: Measures and Results." University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point, 2000.
19. Mushtaq, Rizwan. "Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test." *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 2011. doi:10.2139/ssrn.1911068.
20. Nelson, Daniel B. "Conditional Heteroskedasticity in Asset Returns: A New Approach." *Econometrica*, vol. 59, no. 2, 1991, pp. 347–370. doi:10.2307/2938260.
21. Orabi, Mohammed M. A., and Talal A.-A. Alqurran. "Effect of Volatility Changes on Emerging Stock Markets: The Case of Jordan." *Journal of Management Research*, vol. 7, no. 4, 2015, Article 4.
22. Ormos, Mihaly, and Daniel Timotity. "Asymmetric Volatility in Asset Prices: An Explanation with Mental Framing." *Heliyon*, vol. 10, no. 3, 2024, e24978.
23. Pindyck, Robert S. "The Long-Run Evolution of Energy Prices." *The Energy Journal*, vol. 20, no. 2, 1999, pp. 1–27.
24. Poon, Ser-Huang, and Clive W. J. Granger. "Forecasting Volatility in Financial Markets: A Review." *Journal of Economic Literature*, vol. 41, no. 2, 2003, pp. 478–539. doi:10.1257/002205103765762743.
25. Rana, Shree B. "Dynamics of Time-Varying Volatility in Stock Returns: Evidence from Nepal Stock Exchange." *Journal of Business and Social Sciences Research*, vol. 5, no. 1, 2020, pp. 15–34. doi:10.3126/jbssr.v5i1.30196.
26. Sadorsky, Perry. "Oil Price Shocks and Stock Market Activity." *Energy Economics*, vol. 21, no. 5, 1999, pp. 449–469. doi:10.1016/S0140-9883(99)00020-1.
27. Shiller, Robert J. "Measuring Bubble Expectations and Investor Confidence." *Journal of Psychology and Financial Markets*, vol. 1, no. 1, 2000, pp. 49–60. doi:10.1207/S15327760JPFM0101_05.
28. Tang, Ke, and Wei Xiong. "Index Investment and Financialization of Commodities." *Financial Analysts Journal*, vol. 68, no. 6, 2012, pp. 54–74.
29. Rubio, Villar E. "Using EGARCH Models to Predict Volatility in Unconsolidated Financial Markets: The Case of European Carbon Allowances." *Journal of Environmental Studies and Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 3, 2023, pp. 500–509. doi:10.1007/s13412-023-00828-4.
30. Zakoian, Jean-Michel. "Threshold Heteroskedastic Models." *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, vol. 18, no. 5, 1994, pp. 931–955. doi:10.1016/0165-1889(94)90039-6.